

Valbona Treska¹

Fleura Shkëmbi²

The Role of the Psychologist in the Context of Criminal Assessments and Delinquent Behavior

Abstract

The paper emphasizes the importance of understanding the psychological characteristics and personal attributes that contribute to criminal behavior. It explores various psychological and psycho-social theories that explain delinquent conduct and highlights the role of psychologists in assessing individuals involved in criminal cases. The methodology of the paper involves a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, integrating quantitative and qualitative techniques to gain insights into the psychological profiles of individuals engaged in criminal behavior. The paper discusses the significance of employing a comprehensive approach in psychological assessments, including risk assessments, competency evaluations, and psychological evaluations. Psychologists play a vital role in understanding and evaluating delinquent behavior by utilizing assessment tools and techniques to assess an individual's mental health, cognitive abilities, personality traits, and potential psychological disorders. These evaluations contribute to understanding the underlying factors that influence criminal behavior and inform appropriate interventions or treatment plans. The paper also highlights the ethical considerations involved in criminal assessments, such as obtaining informed consent, maintaining confidentiality, and considering cultural competency. It emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development for assessors to ensure the delivery of high-quality assessments. Furthermore, the paper discusses the role of personal qualities in delinquent behavior, including impulsiveness, the prevalence of negative emotional backdrop, a quest for risky sensations, empathy, altruism, and honesty. It emphasizes the relationship between these personal characteristics and criminal behavior, providing insights into the psychological factors that contribute to delinquency. Overall, this paper aims to explore the crucial role played by psychologists in criminal assessments and understanding delinquent behavior, highlighting the need for a comprehensive approach and ethical considerations in the field of forensic psychology.

Keywords: *Psychological, Psycho-social, Disorders, Criminal assessments, Delinquent behavior*

¹ Department of Psychological Studies, Mediterranean University of Albania, Tirana, Albania, Email: valbona.treska@umsh.edu.al

² Department of Psychological Studies, Mediterranean University of Albania, Tirana, Albania, Email: fleura.shkemi@umsh.edu.al

Introduction

Delinquent behavior is described as a criminal act performed by a human that violates civil society laws. The concept of crime is founded on the idea of normalization, which states that an individual's guilt is determined by the norms and regulations that apply in civil society. Society exercises control over individual behavior not just through legal legislation, but also through ethical and moral values. Crime is a sort of conduct that differs from other types of activity in terms of its contextual weight and the community's perception of it. It is critical to distinguish the characteristics that influence the development of criminal conduct while describing the personal attributes of a deviant personality (Chuasanga & Victoria, 2019). Psychological and psycho-social theories that explain such conduct emphasize an individual's personal attributes and view individual idiosyncrasies as a limiting element in criminal behavior. Another interpretation of criminal conduct is that an offender commits a crime because he or she has not established a suitable attitude toward social reality, which is conditioned by his or her emotions. When discussing the commission of an offense, it is very important to consider the individual psychological characteristics, such as the motivational system and general peculiarities of the activity, which form an individual's general strategy; additionally, it is significant to consider the individual's attitudes. In terms of psychological characteristics, a large number of criminals tend to transfer responsibility onto other offenders and justify themselves in order to prove his/her innocence; this category of criminals attempts to achieve the above-mentioned by exaggerating a victim's guilt, confronting social norms, depreciating social norms, and readdressing responsibility to other/situational factors (McGuire, 2004).

Psychologists and other mental health experts regularly conduct assessments for use in civil and criminal court processes (Melton et al., 2017). In the criminal context, the most common of these assessments are those for competence to stand trial (CST), which refers to the defendant's current ability to understand legal proceedings and to assist his or her lawyer in planning and conducting a defense, and those for criminal responsibility (CR, also known as insanity), which refers to the defendant's mental state at the time of the alleged offense. Despite the fact that these evaluations are performed on a regular basis, there is little information on the standard of practice for these assessments (Gowensmith et al., 2012). The role of psychologists in the context of criminal assessments is crucial in understanding and evaluating the psychological aspects of individuals involved in criminal behavior. Psychologists play a vital role in providing insights into the mental

state, behavior patterns, and underlying factors that contribute to criminal acts. Psychologists employ various assessment tools and techniques to evaluate the psychological functioning of individuals involved in criminal cases. These evaluations help in understanding the individual's mental health, cognitive abilities, personality traits, and potential psychological disorders that may influence their behavior. This paper aims to explore the vital role played by psychologists in criminal assessments and understanding delinquent behavior.

Method

The methodology of this paper involves a comprehensive analysis of existing literature to highlight the importance of employing a comprehensive approach when conducting psychological assessments in the context of criminal assessments and delinquent behavior. The methodology focuses on the integration of quantitative and qualitative techniques and emphasizes the consideration of specific factors related to criminal behavior and delinquency to gain a thorough understanding of individuals' psychological profiles. Relevant studies were identified to highlight the significance of employing a comprehensive approach in psychological assessments. The literature was analyzed to identify key themes related to the comprehensive approach in criminal assessments, including psychological evaluations, risk assessments, competency evaluations, and sentencing recommendations. Additionally, the literature exploration delved into understanding delinquent behavior, including its causes, risk factors, and protective factors.

Understanding Criminal Assessments and Delinquent Behavior

The systematic evaluation of persons involved in criminal proceedings to understand their psychological, behavioral, and cognitive functioning is referred to as criminal evaluation. Criminal evaluations are used to obtain information about a person's mental state, personality features, risk factors, and probable treatment requirements (American Psychological Association [APA], 2013). Psychologists perform these evaluations, which use a variety of assessment instruments, procedures, and standardized measures to collect data and give significant insights into the individual's psychological profile (Mossman, 2013). Criminal assessments serve several purposes, including:

- Risk Assessment: Assessing the risk factors associated with individuals involved in criminal behavior helps to determine the likelihood of future offenses or reoffending. This information assists in making decisions regarding supervision, rehabilitation programs, parole, or release.
- Competency Evaluation: Evaluating an individual's competency to stand trial involves assessing their understanding of legal proceedings, ability to assist in their defense, and capacity to make informed decisions. Competency evaluations help determine if individuals have the cognitive and psychological ability to participate effectively in their legal proceedings.
- Psychological Evaluation: Psychological evaluations provide a comprehensive assessment of an individual's mental health, cognitive abilities, personality traits, and potential psychological disorders. These evaluations contribute to understanding the individual's psychological functioning, identifying factors that may have influenced their criminal behavior, and informing appropriate interventions or treatment plans (Salekin & Lynam, 2010).

Delinquent behavior refers to actions that violate established laws or societal norms, typically committed by individuals who are underage or below the legal age of adulthood. These behaviors are often categorized as criminal offenses when committed by adults. Delinquency can include a wide range of acts, such as theft, vandalism, substance abuse, aggression, truancy, and involvement in gangs. Delinquent behavior is characterized by its deviant nature and potential harm to individuals or society (Piquero et al., 2007).

Psychologists play a critical role in conducting assessments in the context of delinquent behavior. They utilize their expertise in psychological evaluation techniques, standardized assessment tools, and diagnostic criteria to assess the psychological functioning, risk factors, and underlying causes of delinquent behavior in individuals (Salekin, 2008). By conducting comprehensive assessments, psychologists can provide valuable insights into the psychological profiles of delinquents, which inform treatment planning, intervention strategies, and risk management (Falkenbach et al., 2008).

Psychologists are important in understanding delinquent behavior because they do research, analyze data, and use psychological theories to acquire insights into the underlying causes and contributing elements of delinquency. They investigate individual features, environmental factors,

social dynamics, and psychological processes in order to gain a thorough knowledge of why people engage in delinquent conduct (Odgers et al., 2008). Psychologists can help to guide preventative efforts, establish successful intervention programs, and contribute to policy creation by understanding the complexity of delinquency (Snyder & Sickmund, 2006).

The Psychologist's Contribution to Forensic Psychology

The name forensic is derived from the Latin *forensis*, meaning "forum," the site where Roman trials were held. The term *forensic* is now used to signify some engagement of a certain subject of study in a legal arena. There is no universally accepted definition of forensic psychology - many differ. More narrow definitions confine forensic psychology to clinical psychology applications to legal matters (typically in the context of evaluating litigants whose mental states are at issue in legal proceedings), whereas broader definitions include applications of all areas of psychology (clinical, developmental, social, and experimental) to legal matters.

The American Psychological Association's definition of forensic psychology as a specialty provides an example of this narrower scope: *"the professional practice by psychologists within the areas of clinical psychology, counseling psychology, neuropsychology, and school psychology. when they are engaged regularly as experts and represent themselves as such, in an activity primarily intended to provide professional psychological expertise to the judicial system"* (Heilbrun).

Although the origins of forensic psychology may be traced back to the early 1900s, with the application *On the Witness Stand* (Münsterberg, 1908) and the use of mental psychologists in juvenile courts. It will take decades for the discipline to provide the empirical basis required for 10 qualities as an evidence expert lesion on a consistent and unquestionable basis. The application of theory is accepted by both the state and the ally. Both the state and the ally embrace the use of theory, study, and technique to civil and criminal law issues. Doctorates and forensic psychology programs have been created, and postdoctoral scholarships, albeit limited in number, are available. Continuing education programs, provided by APA-approved sponsors, are easily available to give the skills, training, and information necessary in court.

Specialized training and expertise are essential for psychologists to effectively work in the field of criminal assessments and understanding delinquent behavior (Bartol & Bartol, 2021). They require a strong foundation in clinical psychology, as well as additional training and knowledge in forensic psychology and criminology. This specialized training equips psychologists with the skills necessary to assess, evaluate, and provide insights into the psychological factors underlying criminal behavior (Heilbrun et al., 2019).

Ethical Considerations in Criminal Assessments

Criminal evaluations are important in the criminal justice system because they help with the evaluation and decision-making procedures for offenders (APA, 2017). However, the procedure of carrying out these assessments creates serious ethical concerns. To guarantee fairness, truth, and protection of the rights and well-being of the persons involved, ethical rules and principles must be observed.

Obtaining informed permission from the persons being examined is a crucial ethical aspect of criminal examinations. Individuals must provide informed permission if they understand the goal, nature, and potential repercussions of the evaluation and willingly choose to participate. Assessors should offer clear and intelligible information regarding the assessment process, including its purpose, potential risks and benefits, and any limits (Melton et al., 2018). Individuals have the freedom to make autonomous decisions about their involvement with informed consent, which enhances their dignity and respect. Another essential ethical aspect in criminal evaluations is maintaining confidentiality and privacy. Professionals should safeguard assessment data confidentially and guarantee that only authorized personnel have access to the information (Lamberti & Weisman, 2011). Confidentiality is essential for establishing confidence between the assessor and the person being assessed, as well as enabling open and honest communication. It is critical to educate individuals on the boundaries of confidentiality, such as when information must be shared with appropriate parties in order to comply with legal and ethical commitments.

Criminal investigations must be performed with cultural competency, acknowledging and respecting persons' various origins and experiences. Biases can lead to faulty evaluations and unfavorable consequences; therefore, cultural competency guarantees that assessments are fair and unbiased. Assessors should be conscious of their cultural prejudices and work actively to reduce

their influence on the assessment process. To achieve accurate and reliable results across diverse groups, culturally appropriate assessment methods and methodologies should be employed. The competence and training of the specialists performing the evaluations are important ethical factors in criminal assessments. Assessors must have the requisite knowledge, skills, and training to carry out their responsibilities successfully. They must keep current on the newest research and advancements in their area, as well as conform to professional norms and rules. Continuous professional development ensures that assessors keep their expertise and deliver high-quality assessments (Pirelli & Gottdiener, 2018).

Assessments should be carried out in a way that minimizes damage and avoids stigma. Professionals should be aware of the possible psychological influence of the evaluation process on individuals, especially when discussing sensitive material. Measures should be made to safeguard the well-being of those being examined, such as offering assistance or referring them to relevant services when necessary. Furthermore, to avoid unwarranted stigmatization and labeling, assessments should focus on the behavior rather than the individual (Clement et al., 2015).

The Role of Personal Qualities in Delinquent Behavior

Recent research revealed that the Academic Performance Index, i.e., the GPA is a better predictor for delinquent behavior than IQ. There is a correlation between academic achievement and delinquent behavior.

Temperament is an individual characteristic that greatly influences a person's behavioral model. Despite the significant effect of external conditions, it is widely accepted that temperament is influenced by heredity. Character, sociality, activity level, reactivity, and affectivity are all components of temperament. Temperament is important in a child's contact with the environment; hence, the experience obtained in childhood is well represented in his/her environmental attitudes and socialization process at his/her following age development stages. Psychology identifies personal characteristics of an individual that are human psychological attributes. When considering these personal qualities in relation to delinquent behavior, they can be divided into two categories: 1) psychological signs that contribute to an individual's fulfillment of delinquent behavior and 2) psychological signs that prevent an individual from committing any delinquent

behavior. This distinction is necessary to distinguish between personal characteristics that have positive and negative associations with criminal activity (Walsh & Hemmens, 2010).

Impulsiveness is the tendency of an individual to behave without considering the repercussions of his or her actions. Impulsiveness prohibits a person from engaging in intentional conduct. In most circumstances, an impulsive individual's behavior is dictated by the situation; hence, a person can no longer afford to predict the outcome of his or her actions. The study of the association between impulsiveness and delinquent behavior found that in 78 cases out of 80, the relationship between impulsiveness and crime was positive. It should be mentioned that a generally unfavorable emotional background reinforces the link between impulsiveness and delinquent behavior (Lyman, 2018).

Prevalence of negative emotional backdrop - reflects an individual's tendency to analyze incoming situational signals through early annoyance and anger. Background negative emotions substantially correspond with delinquent conduct. This consistency holds true for diverse genders and civilizations. According to the findings, the reason for the negative emotional backdrop is a deficiency of serotonin, a chemical element in the human brain. A lot of experts feel that the absence of this element is a direct predictor of an individual's delinquent conduct (ILIN, 2008).

Quest for risky sensations (low sensitivity threshold) - This attribute is connected to the adoption of active and risk perception, which leads to the individual's quest for risky circumstances. People that are intentionally seeking powerful sentiments while being socialized choose jobs such as firefighters, police officers, and so on, or they engage in extreme sports. Individuals with a poor degree of socialization yet a great drive to seek dangerous sensations - with a high likelihood - prefer to self-realize through carjacking, robbery, and other criminal activities. A review of the literature reveals a very strong positive link between risk demand and crime (Belkania, 2011).

Empathy is the emotional and cognitive ability of an individual to comprehend, experience, and share the feelings and spiritual state of another. The emotional component of empathy allows an individual to experience the anguish of another person, while the cognitive component helps an individual to comprehend the source of the misery. There are those who suffer/bear the anguish of the entire world, while there are others who are unable to understand even the closest person. One of the determinants of criminal behavior is a lack of psychological indication of empathy (Godziashvili, 1998).

Altruism is defined as an individual's care for others and consideration of others' interests without regard for one's own. Altruism, on the other hand, might be considered as a behavioral component of empathy. If a person feels empathy for others, he or she will be encouraged to engage in such behavioral action that would relieve the tension of another person. An examination of these personal characteristics found that a lack of altruism and empathy are closely related to delinquent conduct; the lower the degree of empathy and altruism, the higher the index of anti-social behavior.

Honesty is a psychological characteristic. It consists of specific characteristics such as self-discipline, orderliness, scrupulousness, and responsibility. The development of the aforementioned characteristics is closely related to people's effective adaption to the community. The absence of this characteristic is an impediment to the adaption process.

Acceptability is a personality quality that covers the openness and perceptibility of diverse people's thoughts and ideas. Friendly, respectful, and cooperative interpersonal connections demonstrate acceptance. Trust in individuals is the most significant indicator of acceptance. Individuals with high acceptability can make concessions in the interests of others and assist others. People with this trait are concerned with implementing pro-social conduct and obtaining social desirability (Law, 2014).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the function of psychologists within the framework of criminal assessments and delinquent behavior is multifaceted and critical. Psychologists bring valuable expertise in understanding the psychological factors that contribute to criminal behavior and can assess the state of one's mind, cognitive abilities, and personality traits of individuals involved in the legal system. Their assessments aid in the decision-making processes, such as determining the ability to stand trial, assessing risk for reoffending, and informing appropriate interventions and treatment strategies. Psychologists also play a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs and providing expert testimony in court proceedings. By applying their abilities and knowledge, psychologists help to create a more comprehensive understanding of criminal behavior and encourage the development of evidence-based practices and strategies for prevention, intervention, and rehabilitation. Their involvement underscores the significance of resolving

psychological issues and factors underlying delinquent behavior and promoting a fair and just criminal justice system.

References

- American Psychological Association. (2013). Guidelines for psychological evaluations in child protection matters. *American Psychologist*, 68(1), 1-18.
- American Psychological Association. (2017). Ethical principles of psychologists and code of conduct. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/ethics/code>
- Bartol, C. R., & Bartol, A. M. (2021). *Introduction to forensic psychology: Research and application* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Belkania, N. (2011). *Conscience and Responsibility*. Tbilisi: ATSMKO.
- Chuasanga, A., & Victoria, O. A. (2019). Legal Principles Under Criminal Law in Indonesia Dan Thailand. *Journal Daulat Hukum*, 2(1), 131-138.
- Clement, S., Schauman, O., Graham, T., Maggioni, F., Evans-Lacko, S., Bezborodovs, N., ... & Thornicroft, G. (2015). What is the impact of mental health-related stigma on help-seeking? A systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies. *Psychological medicine*, 45(1), 11-27.
- Enikeev, M. (2005). *Legal Psychology*. Moscow: publishing house NORMA.
- Falkenbach, D. M., Poythress, N. G., & Creevy, C. (2008). The exploration of subtypes of juvenile delinquency with the Psychopathy Checklist: Youth Version. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 35(1), 5-22.
- Godziashvili, I. (1998). *Criminology*. Tbilisi. POLIGRAPHIST.
- Gowensmith, W. N., Murrie, D. C., & Boccaccini, M. T. (2012). Field reliability of competence to stand trial opinions: How often do evaluators agree, and what do judges decide when evaluators disagree? *Law and Human Behavior*, 36(2), 130.
- Heilbrun, K., Grisso, T., & Goldstein, A. M. (2019). *Handbook of psychology, forensic psychology* (2nd ed.). Wiley.
- Hentig, H. V. (1979). *The criminal & His victim*. New York: Yale University Press.
- ILIN, E. (2008). *Motivation and Motives*. Moscow: PITER.
- Lamberti, J. S., & Weisman, R. L. (2011). Ethical considerations in the forensic evaluation of competence to stand trial. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law*, 39(4), 541-550.
- Law, L. (2014). *Nona Todua* (Doctoral dissertation, Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University).
- Lyman, M. D. (2018). *Criminal investigation*. Pearson.
- McGuire, J. (2004). *Understanding psychology and crime: Perspectives on theory and action*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Melton, G. B., Petrila, J., Poythress, N. G., & Slobogin, C. (2018). *Psychological evaluations for the courts: A handbook for mental health professionals and lawyers* (4th ed.). Guilford Press.
- Melton, G. B., Petrila, J., Poythress, N. G., Slobogin, C., Otto, R. K., Mossman, D., & Condie, L. O. (2017). *Psychological evaluations for the courts: A handbook for mental health professionals and lawyers*. Guilford Publications.

- Mossman, D. (2013). Assessing predictions of violence: Being accurate about accuracy. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 81*(4), 631-643.
- Odgers, C. L., Moffitt, T. E., Broadbent, J. M., Dickson, N., Hancox, R. J., Harrington, H., ... & Caspi, A. (2008). Female and male antisocial trajectories: From childhood origins to adult outcomes. *Development and Psychopathology, 20*(2), 673-716.
- Piquero, A. R., Farrington, D. P., & Blumstein, A. (2007). Key issues in criminal career research: New analyses of the Cambridge Study in Delinquent Development. Cambridge University Press.
- Pirelli, G., & Gottdiener, W. H. (2018). The ethical challenges of forensic psychiatry: Assessments, access, advocacy, and amelioration. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law, 46*(2), 181-193.
- Salekin, R. T. (2008). Psychopathy in children and adolescents: The need for a developmental perspective. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology, 36*(2), 271-275.
- Salekin, R. T., & Lynam, D. R. (2010). Child and adolescent psychopathy: Assessment issues and treatment needs. In T. J. Crowley, R. R. Watson, & D. J. Eiden (Eds.), *Psychopathy: Risk factors, behavioral symptoms and treatment approaches* (pp. 75-98). Nova Science Publishers.
- Snyder, H. N., & Sickmund, M. (2006). Juvenile offenders and victims: 2006 national report. US Department of Justice, Office of Justice Programs, Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention.
- Walsh, A., & Hemmens, C. (2010). *Introduction to criminology: A text/reader*. Sage.